

Platform aware scheduling on Kubernetes

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PROJECT SPECIFICATION

Motivation

Addressing energy consumption in CERN's data centre, virtual machines and kubernetes clusters holds multifaceted significance. Notably, it aligns with CERN's commitment to environmental stewardship, as efficient energy usage directly reduces the facility's carbon footprint and promotes sustainability. Beyond ecological benefits, optimising energy consumption translates into substantial cost savings by curbing operational expenses related to power usage. This focus on resource efficiency extends to enhancing the utilisation of computing assets, thereby extracting maximum value from the available infrastructure. Moreover, managing energy consumption safeguards the seamless continuity of research endeavours, ensuring that computing resources remain dependable and available for the pursuit of high-energy physics studies. In this pursuit, CERN's attention to energy efficiency not only underscores its dedication to cutting-edge research but also serves as a model for other institutions aiming to harmonise scientific progress with responsible resource management. Through innovative energy practices, CERN can maintain operational excellence, adhere to regulatory standards, and inspire a global movement towards sustainable scientific exploration.

ABSTRACT

Platform-aware scheduling in Kubernetes refers to the practice of intelligently assigning workloads (pods) to nodes in a Kubernetes cluster based on the specific characteristics and capabilities of the nodes and the resource requirements of the pods. The objective is to visualise and help to optimise resource utilisation, performance, and other relevant metrics while considering the heterogeneity of the cluster.

There are many tools available. Tools like

- Kepler (<https://sustainable-computing.io/>)
- Scaphandre (<https://github.com/hubblo-org/scaphandre>)

This project explores the concept of platform-aware scheduling in Kubernetes, focusing on visualising energy consumption metrics to optimise resource allocation and performance in future. The goal is to visualise different metrics related to power consumption in a cluster using kepler and help to design an intelligent scheduler that considers the heterogeneous nature of the Kubernetes cluster, the diverse resource requirements of containers, and the dynamic nature of workloads. By employing the Kepler library and other relevant tools, the project aims to enhance the energy efficiency, scalability, and fault tolerance of containerized applications. The research involves studying different power consumption, resource allocation and other related metrics, analysing pod affinity and anti-affinity rules, and incorporating QoS levels to find an optimal balance between power consumption and performance. The results of this project will contribute to the advancement of sustainable computing in Kubernetes-based environments, making strides towards more efficient and eco-friendly data centre operations.

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1. Introduction

All facets of a business, including IT operations, now place a high focus on sustainability. Kubernetes clusters are a large energy consumer, thus IT operations teams need to pay close attention to where and what is using the most energy in order to manage energy efficiency and be environmentally conscientious. But many teams don't know how to measure pod energy use or overall energy consumption.

The idea that we had for this project was to try different tools to get energy consumption metrics at virtual machine level and visualise those data. I tried both kepler and Scaphandre library but later I continued with kepler because of its richness and metrics estimation capability when power measurement tools are not available in virtual machines.

2. Tools

2.1 Kepler

Kepler (Kubernetes-based Efficient Power Level Exporter) uses eBPF to probe energy related system stats and exports as Prometheus metrics [1]. eBPF can run sandboxed programs in a privileged context such as the operating system kernel. It is used to safely and efficiently extend the capabilities of the kernel without requiring to change kernel source code or load kernel modules. Kepler collects data at the kernel level so that the energy can be attributed to processes with as much transparency as possible. Once Kepler collects the data, it is exported into Prometheus to translate the metrics into readable dashboards to help make energy conservation decisions. In addition, Kepler uses regression and machine learning models to estimate future energy consumption and improve accuracy. Kepler also makes an energy consumption and carbon emissions dashboard to display the carbon footprint per pod. Which is excellent to provide energy-aware pod scheduling and node tuning.

Figure 2.1: Component and architecture of kepler [2]

Kepler consists of 3 major components: exporter, estimator sidecar, and model server. Kepler Estimator functions as a sidecar for Kepler Exporter, a client module to the Kepler model server. The primary function of the Kepler Model Server is to return a power estimating model that matches the request and includes the target granularity (node overall, node for each processor component, pod overall, pod for each processor component), accessible input metrics, and model filters like accuracy.

2.2 Prometheus

Prometheus is an open-source monitoring and alerting toolkit designed for gathering time-series metrics from various sources, storing them efficiently, and enabling real-time querying and analysis. Originally developed by SoundCloud, Prometheus has become a widely adopted tool within the cloud-native and DevOps communities. It offers a flexible and scalable solution for monitoring complex distributed systems, including applications, services, and infrastructure. With a powerful query language and data provided from kepler library, Prometheus allows us to gain valuable insights from its own data and also from data exported by kepler into the performance and health of the kubernetes cluster, facilitating proactive monitoring and efficient incident response.

2.3 Grafana

Grafana is a widely-used open-source platform designed for visualising and monitoring time-series data. It provides a user-friendly interface that allows users to create interactive and customizable dashboards, graphs, and charts from various data sources such as databases, APIs, Prometheus, and other monitoring tools. Grafana's flexibility and extensive plugin ecosystem make it a versatile tool for organisations seeking to gain insights from their data, track performance metrics, and make informed decisions. We use it to visualise metrics generated by kepler, Grafana simplifies the process of turning

complex metrics into meaningful visual representations, contributing to enhanced data-driven decision-making processes in platform -aware scheduling.

3. Kepler Architecture

3.1 Kepler Exporter

As mentioned earlier, Kepler exporter uses eBPF programs to get metrics from kernel level and when it gets the metrics, those metrics are exported to Prometheus. Kepler exporter exports a variety of container metrics to Prometheus related to different feature, such as Container Energy Consumption, Container resource utilisation, Hardware counter metrics, cgroups metrics, Kubelet metrics, IRQ metrics, Metrics for Node information, Metrics for Node energy consumption [3]. Where the main ones are those related to energy consumption.

Kepler requires RAPL (Running average power limit) and ACPI (Advanced Configuration and Power Interface) to generate metrics related to energy consumption. Which were not available while doing this project and those metrics are estimated using the Kepler Estimator and Model server.

3.2 Kepler Estimator

Kepler offers 2 types of estimators, Local Linear Regression Estimator and General Estimator Sidecar. During this project both types of estimators were tested. Local Linear Regression Estimator estimates power using the trained weights multiplied by normalised value of usage metrics (Linear Regression Model). The Kepler General Estimator serves as a client module to the Kepler Model Server, running as a sidecar of the Kepler Exporter's main container. It handles PowerRequests and interacts with the power estimation models to provide power consumption estimates such as `kepler_container_joules_total`, `kepler_container_dram_joules_total`, etc. The estimator converts the usage metrics and applies them to trained models, which can be any neural network from Keras (TensorFlow) or any regression model from the Scikit-Learn library.

Kepler estimator can be deployed in 4 different way.

3.2.1 Minimum Deployment

The minimum deployment is to use a local linear regression estimator in Kepler main container with only offline-trained model weights [4].

3.2.2 Deployment with General Estimator Sidecar

Unlike the local estimator, the general estimator sidecar is instrumented with several inference-supportive libraries and dependencies. Although this adds an additional overhead, it pays off given the increased estimation accuracy. [4].

3.2.3 Minimum deployment connecting to Kepler Model Server

To get the updated weights, which are expected to provide better estimation accuracy, Kepler may connect to a remote Kepler Model Server that performs online training using data from the system with the power measuring tool [4].

3.2.4 Full deployment

The deployment of the Kepler General Estimator is depicted in the accompanying figure, along with a connection to Kepler Model Server. The Estimator is capable of changing its model on the fly, by requesting from the Model Server the most recent and accurate model based on the particularities of the request [4].

Figure 3.2: Architecture of kepler estimator in full deployment Scenario[3]

3.3 Kepler Model Server

Power model training and serving are made easier by the Kepler model server, a side project of Kepler. This makes it possible to use the Kepler ecosystem to gather data from one environment, train a power model using a pipeline structure, and feed that data to another environment where a power metre (a device for measuring energy) is not present. Model server downloads pre trained models from kepler_model_db another side project of kepler. Based on the best model requested by the estimator it returns power metrics to the estimator.

4. Installation

The project was designed to be easily installed, and provides multiple ways to do so:

- using an existing helm chart [5]
- building manifests with make [5]
- using the Kepler operator [6]

We tried all installation options. While all methods should work out of the box, we encountered a few issues and settled on building the manifests using make. The command used is:

```
make build-manifest OPTS="PROMETHEUS_DEPLOY ESTIMATOR_SIDECAR_DEPLOY  
MODEL_SERVER_DEPLOY"
```

More configuration options can be found in the documentation [7].

5. Testing with Workload

To test how Kepler is able to export power metrics in different scenarios, stress-ng is used. Stress ng is a stress generator, the stress-ng tool loads and stresses defined nodes in a cluster. It contains a wide variety of stressors, often known as stress mechanisms.

```
apiVersion: v1  
kind: Pod  
metadata:  
  name: stress-ng-0  
  namespace: kepler  
spec:  
  containers:  
  - name: stress-ng  
    image: polinux/stress-ng  
    command: ["sleep", "inf"]  
    resources:  
      limits:  
        memory: "4G"  
      requests:  
        memory: "2G"
```

With the above config map I use commands listed below to stress cluster.

- stress-ng --cpu 4 --timeout 60s --metrics-brief
- stress-ng --disk 2 --timeout 60s --metrics-brief
- stress-ng --cpu 10 --io 2 --vm 10 --vm-bytes 1G --timeout 10m --metrics-brief

Kepler estimator produced metrics in different test case scenarios and with use of grafana dashboard i visualise graphs and spikes in data when test cases are performed.

Figure 4: Grafana dashboard when test case are performed

5. Results

Kepler produces metrics and we can visualise those metrics in the grafana dashboard. Kepler is able to generate pod and node level energy consumption. Carbon footprint tracking at the node and pod level using tools like Kepler plays a pivotal role in understanding and mitigating the environmental impact of running applications in kubernetes clusters. By monitoring resource consumption and energy usage at these granular levels, we can gain insights into the carbon emissions associated with pod or level operations. This data-driven approach enables us to make informed decisions about resource allocation, workload optimization, and infrastructure design, ultimately leading to a reduction in energy consumption and carbon emissions.

6. Conclusions and Future Work

In conclusion, engaging in a summer project focused on platform-aware scheduling using the Kepler library has proven to be a highly productive and valuable endeavour. This project has brought to light the substantial correlation between technology and environmental sustainability by exploring energy consumption metrics and carbon footprint data within Kubernetes clusters, both at the node and pod levels. Some future directions to look into power aware scheduling:

- Platform-aware-scheduling [8]
- Peaks [9]

The gathered information not only emphasises the value of prudent resource management and task management, but also opens the way for careful judgement in the field of digital operations. With the aid of these insightful discoveries, efforts may now be directed towards improving the effectiveness and performance of Kubernetes clusters while reducing their ecological impact.

References

1. Kubernetes Efficient Power Level Exporter (Kepler). Available at: <https://sustainable-computing.io/> (Accessed: 2 July 2023).
2. Components Components - Kepler. Available at: <https://sustainable-computing.io/design/architecture/> (Accessed: 28 July 2023).
3. Monitoring container power consumption with Kepler - Kepler. Available at: <https://sustainable-computing.io/design/metrics/> (Accessed: 8 August 2023).
4. Kepler power estimation deployment - Kepler. Available at: https://sustainable-computing.io/kepler_model_server/power_estimation/ (Accessed: 8 August 2023).
5. Deploy using Manifests - Kepler. Available at: <https://sustainable-computing.io/installation/kepler/> (Accessed: 5 August 2023).
6. Kepler Operator on Kind - kepler Available at: <https://sustainable-computing.io/installation/kepler-operator/> (Accessed: 5 August 2023).
7. Nurturing Sustainability: Raising Power Consumption Awareness -cern Available at: <https://kubernetes.docs.cern.ch/blog/2023/09/05/nurturing-sustainability-raising-power-consumption-awareness/> (Accessed: 5 August 2023).
8. PEAKS: Power Efficiency Aware Kubernetes Scheduler - sustainable-computing-io. Available at: <https://github.com/sustainable-computing-io/peaks> (Accessed: 28 August 2023).
9. Platform Aware Scheduling - intel. Available at: <https://github.com/intel/platform-aware-scheduling> (Accessed: 28 August 2023).